

Journalistic Curation of Science Videos

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Abstract

The web portal SciViews.de, operated by the German popular science publishing house Spektrum der Wissenschaft, focuses on curating popular science web videos. The editors, following journalistic guidelines, select and embed videos from a variety of sources, commission short journalistic reviews and present the videos to the public. The heterogeneity of science videos found on the web is very high. Experiences from curating science videos for SciViews indicate that, in general, such videos are a great enrichment for science communication but often lack journalistic qualities and tend to be, in themselves, poor sources of information. Given the important role of science communication for society, this observation should raise serious concerns. Shortness and entertaining qualities, however, which are often considered to be important for the attractiveness of videos, may not play such an important role after all, as experience shows.

Keywords: science communication, science journalism, science video, popular science web video, content curation, YouTube

1. Introduction

What do we know about popular science web videos on the basis of scientifically sound data instead of anecdotal evidence? Not that much. "Still very little is known on what kind of scientific content can be found on YouTube and other online-sharing websites, who produces and uploads it, and how various users makes sense of it and perceive various types of content on video websites," states Joachim Allgaier, media researcher at the University of Klagenfurt (Allgaier, 2016a: 4).

That being said, the field is developing rapidly. In German-speaking countries more and more conferences on media science and science communication have been addressing the topic¹, indicating that science communication – including science journalism, science blogging and institutional science communication or science PR – via web video is playing an increasingly important role.

In this article our goal is to offer valuable insights on popular science web videos – science videos, for short –, which we derive from a specific perspective not as researchers but as science editors and curators. The German publisher Spektrum der Wissenschaft Verlagsgesellschaft, which

¹ Recent conferences in German-speaking countries addressing amongst other things the issue of science videos include the International Conference on Science, Research and Popular Culture, Klagenfurt, 2015 (jcom.sissa.it/international-conference-science-research-and-popular-culture-klagenfurt-austria-17-18-september), 15th Annual STS Conference Graz 2016 – Critical Issues in Science, Technology and Society Studies (conference.aau.at/event/46/page/16) and Wissen in Bewegung, Karlsruhe, 2015 (www.wissen-in-bewegung.net). The 20th International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, Hannover (www.tpd12016.org) will be held in September this year.

specialises in popular science media, operates SciViews.de², a commercial website dedicated to journalistically curating science videos. A small editorial team selects embeddable videos from the web according to a set of loosely defined yet rigorous criteria.

These videos are embedded on SciViews – giving due credit to the rights holders and to the hosting platforms – and presented to the users, either in the form of short introductory texts or of reviews written by science journalists, science bloggers or SciViews editors. From a subjective but scientifically competent and journalistic perspective these authors highlight the positive and negative aspects of the videos and assess their content in a broader scientific context. Lastly, the content is tagged, categorized, supplemented with useful links, and optimised for search engine discoverability.

The prerequisite for the existence and continuing operation of SciViews is a sustainable business model. We describe it briefly, because it has some impact on how SciViews editors curate content. SciViews enters into commercial partnerships with, among others, renowned research institutions that are engaged in the production of science videos as part of their science communication activities and aim at presenting them – via SciViews and its partner site Spektrum.de³ – to a broader audience. For these partners it is not only vital to find a larger audience but also to present their institutions in an environment characterised by editorially and journalistically high-quality

² SciViews.de was founded in 2015 by the author, Thilo Körkel.

³ Spektrum.de is visited by 940.000 users per month (unique users according to AGOF digital facts / 04-2016, 14+ years old).

content. This expectation obviously corresponds with the high editorial standards at Spektrum der Wissenschaft in general.

2. The curation of science videos: key aspects

Journalistic curation criteria

For a video to be selected for SciViews it should ideally fulfil general journalistic criteria – which include, but are not limited to, providing truthful, accurate and impartial information – as well as criteria specific to SciViews. The latter are continuously discussed in the editors' team but have not been codified yet; accordingly, the following explanations are only an approximation of SciViews' editorial practice.

The videos selected for SciViews must belong to the realm of popular science including more serious content – like full lectures or in-depth explanations of scientific phenomena –, and must be relevant and worth watching. Their sources must be trustworthy. Unknown sources are checked and taken into account if they provide serious content. Videos must be technically embeddable on SciViews. The language used, either spoken or in the form of subtitles, should be German or English.

Videos are preferably selected for SciViews when they describe a scientific fact of relevance at the cutting edge of scientific knowledge. The selection process presupposes a scientifically interested user; the videos are not intended to spark laypeople's interest in science (as is often defined as a goal by science communicators).

Furthermore, videos on SciViews should seek to explain scientific facts to some degree instead of avoiding the complexities of the respective issue. Videos that have special functions beyond journalistic interest – which e.g. are produced to convey certain ideological messages, to uncritically promote an institution or technology or to merely inspire enthusiasm –, while failing to

properly represent the scientific content are usually discarded (or critically reviewed).

If one or more of these requirements are not met, but the video is still selected for SciViews, the reviewer is expected to point out the respective weaknesses.

Criteria specific to film production – the quality of directing, acting, writing, editing and so forth – are of lesser importance for SciViews editors, since their main focus is not on the medium of film but on the communication of science.

Many science videos, perhaps even the majority of science videos on the web, were not produced with journalistic intentions. But as they are available to virtually everyone it is desirable for the user – and hence for the society as a whole whose members search for information and entertainment related to science and technology – to know if one can rely on the video being truthful, accurate, impartial and so forth. Users should also be informed if the video fulfils non-journalistic functions which might come along with lower standards. This is why SciViews editors consistently apply journalistic criteria, even to those videos that don't seem to have been produced with journalistic intentions.

Insights from reviews and editorial practice

By July 2016 more than 400 SciViews reviews, i.e. short texts (typically 1,000 to 3,000 characters long) containing judgmental statements with respect to certain aspects of a video, had been published. This amount of texts offers a number of representative insights into core aspects of science videos when considered from a journalistic point of view. Additional insights come from videos discarded by the editors because of quality deficits.

Negative aspects of science videos include the following:

- A video neglects the fact that the scientific advance or insight that it reports upon has specific limits in significance. Examples for such limits: An insight in biomedicine cannot be applied to humans, some new knowledge only applies to very special circumstances, or some advanced technique is highly controversial from an ethical point of view.
- A video lacks information contextualizing the topic presented. Examples: Is the topic part of a more general development in science? Are the methods or insights presented attributable to a specific team or lab, or are there competitors? Are there controversial aspects or ethical issues related to it?
- A video that reports on advances in established fields spends effort on explaining well-known basics instead of highlighting the recent advances, which are what actually justified the production of the video.
- A video does not present independent sources.
- A video displays deficits in the quality of content.
- Entertaining aspects of a video – often including speed talk and rapid animations – seem to reduce the quality of content and/or comprehensibility.
- A video or its immediate environment does not convey information about its source or the intention of its producers.

Another undesirable aspect of science communication via web video, though one not obvious from analysing SciViews reviews, is the phenomenon that some disciplines of science are underrepresented by science videos or even are not represented at all. The reason for this is simple: Topics which are

difficult to visualize – for example when related to mathematics, informatics, quantum physics or material science – are not very likely to be presented in film. Although underrepresentation of certain topics in science communication also applies to other media such as magazine articles this effect seems to be even more pronounced in the field of video.

More important, and also not obvious from analysing reviews, is the question whether the existing science videos sufficiently cover topics of high societal relevance which would be desirable from a journalistic point of view.

Naturally enough, the fact that science videos on the web often lack journalistic qualities is not surprising. Journalistic work, put in the production of science web videos, simply does not pay off at present. This circumstance, however, should be a source of concern, given the important functions of science communication for a society as discussed e.g. by German science academies (Deutsche Akademie der Technikwissenschaften et al., 2014), and the fact that web usage increasingly relies on video content.

Coverage

In a German study on science communication released five years ago (Gerber, 2011), science videos still weren't even mentioned. The same holds true for a study published three years later (Deutsche Akademie der Technikwissenschaften et al., 2014). Since then, however, the importance of science communication via web video has clearly grown. While there is a dearth of reliable research data, some more general comments about the situation in Germany can be made.

Today the use of videos, while already consolidating in some fields, is still on the rise. In Germany, 32 per cent of 14- to 29-year-old so-called onliners use video portals on a daily basis (Kupferschmitt, 2015: 386). Particularly young men, the study says, display habitual consumption behaviour, as a result of

which video consumption on YouTube, Facebook and elsewhere in this age group is now higher than TV consumption (Kupferschmitt, 2015: 390).

A recent study (Wissenschaft im Dialog & TNS Emnid, 2016) focussing on science communication shows that 44 per cent of those interviewed who seek information about research and science in the internet use YouTube or similar video platforms for this purpose. In the age group between 14 and 29 years this number is as high as 78 per cent.

Samplings of YouTube and elsewhere, conducted at random by the author, show that science videos are of growing importance for scientific institutions in Germany including universities, excellence clusters, research institutions, EU-funded projects and others. Newspapers and magazines, too, are increasingly engaging in this field (Moebus, 2016). For several years now, two major web video contests in Germany⁴ have promoted science communication via web video and offered workshops and seminars. Germany's Robert Bosch Foundation, which engages in science journalism, recently funded an e-Book on the topic (Körkel & Hoppenhaus, 2016).

Also on the rise – though usually not in the realm of popular science – are video abstracts accompanying scientific publications (Spicer, 2012).

Particularly impressive is the success of science videos in the English-speaking world. Some science YouTubers⁵ attract millions of subscribers and count

⁴ The most prominent web video competitions in Germany are Fast Forward Science (www.fastforwardscience.de, since 2013) and Foresight Filmfestival (www.foresight-filmfestival.de, since 2015). The predecessor of Foresight, Nanospots.de, dates back to 2012.

⁵ Some of the international YouTube channels with more than one million subscribers and more than one hundred million views are www.youtube.com/scishow, www.youtube.com/1veritasium, www.youtube.com/AsapSCIENCE and www.youtube.com/numberphile.

hundreds of millions of video views, while TED channels⁶ reach even higher numbers of views. At a lower level, major research institutions also draw a large audience⁷ especially when dealing with appealing scientific topics like space flight.

However, the success of some channels cannot be taken as representative for the field of science communication as a whole. As YouTube professionals (Krachten, 2016) and media researchers (Welbourne & Grant, 2015) point out for the special case of science YouTubers, their impact is due to their personalities, their authentic behaviour, their excellence in storytelling and their intensive interaction with the community on social platforms. These features cannot easily be replicated by the video production departments of science magazines or scientific institutions.

For German-language science videos, in particular, it is hardly the case that they easily find their audience. Clearly, there are some outstanding channels with up to several million views⁸. But most videos stay below the threshold of

⁶ The conference organisation TED (Technology, Entertainment, Design) is famous for the so-called TED Talks on scientific, cultural and academic topics. Video recordings of TED Talks have been viewed billions of times.

⁷ The most prominent of NASA's channels, www.youtube.com/NASATElevision, counts close to one million subscribers and 100 million views. The most prominent ESA channel (www.youtube.com/ESA) has about 150,000 subscribers and 40 million views. Numbers retrieved 7 August 2016.

⁸ Some of the German-language YouTube channels with currently several tens to several hundred thousand subscribers and several million views are www.youtube.com/100SekundenPhysik, www.youtube.com/Clixoom, www.youtube.com/KurzgesagtDE. The strikingly high numbers of the Clixoom channel, with 350,680 subscribers and 115,734,264 views (retrieved 31 July 2016), are mostly due to the fact that the channel had started in 2008 presenting interviews with celebrities before in 2013 channel owner Christoph Krachten dedicated it to covering science topics.

public perception, even when promoted by a countrywide science video competition⁹.

The slightly surprising fact that some German institutional channels reach relatively high view numbers¹⁰ is due to the fact that they present videos not only in German but also in the universal language English, that they cover science topics of global interest, and that they present a relatively high number of videos.

Do web videos need to be short and entertaining?

Among media workers it is sometimes taken for granted that web videos need to be short and entertaining to be attractive for users and to reach a relevant number of viewers. "Short" usually means that videos should have a length of between one and two – or maximum three – minutes.

It may be true that there are many examples of very short and very successful web videos. But there are also some indications that shortness is not so decisive and not always desirable.

An analysis (Pew Research Center, 2012) of news videos on YouTube, performed by the Pew Research Center, found that "half of the most popular videos were more than two minutes, and 18% were longer than five minutes" (Pew Research Center, 2012: 26). Furthermore the study states that length often adds to quality. Longer videos tend to show more features – like video

⁹ The web video competition Fast Forward Science is organised by Wissenschaft im Dialog and is supported by Stifterverband für die Deutsche Wissenschaft. The winning video in the category Substanz for 2015, "Constraints on the Universe as a Numerical Simulation", www.youtube.com/watch?v=68hb7aGeCzg, is approaching 3,000 views (retrieved 24 July 2016).

¹⁰ Examples of institutional science channels with relatively large audiences are www.youtube.com/DLRde (owned by German Aerospace Center, 8,688 subscribers, 2,232,185 views) and www.youtube.com/MaxPlanckSociety (owned by the German research organisation Max Planck Society, 10,519 subscribers, 2,767,192 views). Numbers retrieved 31 July 2016.

recordings from people or sceneries instead of graphic images – or include controversial opinions.

Based on their study focussing on science communication (Welbourne & Grant, 2015a) the authors state in a related news article: "Lastly, your videos should be as long as necessary. But, your videos do not need to be less than 5 minutes, as is sometimes suggested" (Welbourne & Grant, 2015b). The authors add that they found no relationship between video length and number of views.

A random sample of the YouTube channel minutephysics¹¹ shows that the sixty seconds for explaining physics phenomena, a limit originally envisaged by the channel, usually are not enough. Only two of the six most recent videos were less than three minutes long (2:55 resp. 2:48 minutes), one of them was as long as 5:17 minutes. Actually, successful videos with a length of even ten minutes can easily be found¹².

The experience from curating videos for SciViews, too, shows that videos shorter than two minutes often are less likely to be selected, since they often have drawbacks, mostly in terms of their information content. They can visually enrich some given information but are, in general, not able to provide that information themselves.

Entertainment qualities are also considered by some to be an important criterion for the coverage and success of a video. A recent study (Nitz, 2016), however, shows differentiated results. Two film versions about a scientific topic – one of them considered to be entertaining, the other one news-like and focussing on objectively presenting its content – were presented to test

¹¹ Video lengths from www.youtube.com/minutephysics retrieved 31 July 2016.

¹² Among others, the channel www.youtube.com/scishow provides some examples.

viewers. Entertaining elements, the study claims, can have a negative effect on the viewers' assessment of the films, especially when they have to assess the information content. Another finding from the study showed that users tended to like the neutral version more (Nitz, 2016: 7).

Moreover, the study states that the quality of a video is not limited to be an intrinsic quality of the video itself but also lies in the eye of the beholder. When asked to focus on relevance and entertainment value, those viewers who had displayed an interest in the topic presented or were used to consuming media content on science and knowledge rated the quality of a video much more positively than other viewers did.

Considering these findings, the study comes to a conclusion that may prove useful for science communicators: Normative quality standards, the author claims, are to a large extent congruent to the expectations of the viewers (Nitz 2016: 7).

Another recent study (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2016), focussing on general news, indicates that a user's decision for the consumption of a video is predominantly governed by other criteria than video length. The most important reason for users to resist video seems to be a lack of confidence in the medium: 78 per cent of the respondents, asked about their habits when consuming news, claimed that they rely more on text than on video.

The study also found that 41 per cent of the respondents, when asked to give reasons for not consuming more video, argued that text news can be consumed more quickly and conveniently (Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism, 2016: 7). However, this number may be significantly lower when science topics come into play. It is reasonable to expect that consumers

appreciate videos more when they promise to support comprehension of complex matters.

Science videos as sources of information

Videos are popular among science communicators, as they promise to reach a wider public and to exert fascination on their audience. However, these potential benefits also entail some problems for science communication in general, and for the way science is perceived in the public.

One of the issues is that, in some respects, videos tend to be a poor source of information. Among the problematic aspects are:

Publication date: An indicated publication date of a web video may not be the date of its first publication. The video may have been published, for secondary or tertiary exploitation, on different channels at different dates. So the indicated date might only be a proxy for the date when the given information was topical.

Topicality: A "timeless" video tends to profit from the so called long tail traffic, that is, from audiences watching the video well after its publication. Accordingly, some videos intentionally do not mention dates or time-specific contextual information.

Source of scientific information: A video may mention anonymous "scientists" without providing further information on their affiliation or whether their research was peer reviewed before being published. So, the relevance and trustworthiness of this video remain unclear to the viewer.

Function of the video: In case of some videos it remains unclear exactly what type of video it is. Is it corporate or institutional PR? Is it a piece of science journalism? Is it laypersons' work? and so forth. Here, too, the relevance and trustworthiness of the video remain unclear to the viewer. A special problem arises when the function of a video is to promote anti- or pseudo-scientific

content including climate change denial, views of creationists or of the anti-immunization lobby. In these cases, which are frequent (Allgaier, 2016b), it may remain unclear to a lay user whether a video conveys the scientific consensus or whether it gives erroneous information or deliberately spreads misleading information.

Depth of scientific content: Some videos have strengths in visual expression, in storytelling, or in triggering emotions, but not necessarily in the depth of scientific information, factuality or completeness.

3. Conclusions

Popular science videos are on the rise. However, when it comes to assessing individual instances of the entirety of publicly available science videos from a journalistic perspective – as is the editorial practice at SciViews.de, a platform for the curation of science videos –, severe journalistic deficits become apparent. A significant proportion of videos even seem to promote anti-science views (Allgaier, 2016b).

Science videos as an element of science communication should, among other things, provide societies and their individual members with truthful, accurate and impartial information, thus enhancing the knowledge of the population and providing a basis for discussing science related decisions which may affect the future of these societies. From the findings presented here it is obvious that, in general, the current offering of science videos on the web does not fulfil these expectations in a satisfactory manner.

Disclosure of competing interests:

The author is an employee of Spektrum der Wissenschaft Verlagsgesellschaft, Heidelberg, Germany and responsible for the operation of SciViews.de, a

commercial platform for the curation of science videos, owned by Spektrum der Wissenschaft. Some of the institutions mentioned in this article are potential or actual customers or cooperation partners of SciViews.

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